

soil with ECe 7.4 mmho/cm at 3 soil moisture levels: airdried, -3 bar soil water potential (20% moisture), and waterlogged. Both experiments were in three replications. Except in the first 24 h, volatilization rate was measured at 48-h intervals. Soil and floodwater pH (1:2) were 7.5 and 8.2 before fertilizer application.

Except with UB and UPP, volatilization nearly doubled at 7.5 mmho/cm (Fig. 1). Figure 2 shows that the loss from both PU and AS increased with increasing soil moisture.

Volatilization was greatest during the first 3-7 d, and then gradually declined.

Results showed that N use efficiency could be improved by reducing volatilization in salt-affected lowland rice fields by applying PU instead of AS, and by placing PU 5 cm deep in soil as UPP or UB. For upland fields, fertilizer application should be timed so that soil moisture is low during and immediately following N application. *ℒ*

2. Volatilization loss of NH₃ at 3 soil moisture levels, West Bengal, India.

Response of rainfed rice to post-planting soil-management practices

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We studied the response of rainfed rice (VRS16) to 4 postemergence management practices: minimum tillage, interrow compaction at Proctor moisture content to achieve bulk densities of 1.6

and 1.8 g/cm³, embedding polythene strips in the interrow space, and conventional practices. Soil was a loamy sand with 0.44% organic C, bulk density of 1.36 g/cm³, and saturated hydraulic conductivity of 45 mm/h. Rice was sown in rows spaced at 23 cm on 6 Jul 1984. It received a basal application of 20-18-33 kg NPK/ha and topdressing of 20 kg N/ha 45 d after sowing. Treatments were imposed after complete crop emergence.

All soil modifications significantly increased grain yield as compared to the conventional practices (see table). Grain yield was highest when the interrow soil was compacted to a bulk density of 1.6 g/cm³. Embedding polythene strips between the rows also was promising. Compacting the soil to a bulk density greater than 1.6 g/cm³ reduced grain yield, possibly by restricting root proliferation. Straw yield did not differ significantly among treatments. *ℒ*

Rice grain and straw yield with different soil management practices, Almora, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	Grain	Straw
Minimum tillage	1.9	4.7
Compaction at Proctor moisture content to bulk density of 1.6 g/cm ³	2.0	5.1
Compaction at Proctor moisture content to bulk density of 1.8 g/cm ³	1.7	4.7
Embedding polythene strips in the interrow space	1.9	5.0
Conventional practices	1.4	4.1
CD at 5%	0.3	ns

Influence of N level and source on rice yield

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We evaluated prilled urea (PU), urea supergranules (USG), and 1% PPD urea (PPDU) in a field experiment with Co 43 at TNAU. N levels were 0, 37.5, 75.0, and 112.5 kg/ha. P, K, and Zn were applied basally at 17.6, 33.2, and 2.3 kg/ha. USG was applied at 8-10 cm depth and PU and PPDU were applied

in 3 splits. Soil was a clay (Typic Haplustalf) with pH 8.4, E.C. 0.2 mmho/cm, 107-9.8-263 ppm available NPK, 588 ppm total soil N, and 0.78% organic C.

Grain yield and crop performance were generally best with USC (see table). Plants recovered more N from USG, followed by PPDU and PU. N recovery ratio was higher at lower application rates. Postharvest soil analysis indicated that total N content did not change significantly, although USG plots had a maximum 729 ppm total N. *ℒ*

Influence of N source and level on grain yield and plant characters, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Tillers		Height		Grains (no./Panicle)	Straw yield		Grain yield		N use efficiency	Total soil N at harvest
	no./ m ²	Increase over control (%)	cm	Increase over control (%)		t/ha	Increase over control (%)	t/ha	Increase over control (%)		
Control – no N PU	13	–	25	–	149	5.8	–	1.7	–	–	588
37.5	15	14	28	10	159	6.6	13	3.0	76	35	697
75.0	18	40	29	15	164	8.6	48	3.4	98	23	728
112.5	16	23	29	15	170	9.2	59	4.2	142	22	735
Av	16	25	28	13	164	8.1	40	3.5	105	24	720
USG											
37.5	16	28	29	15	169	8.0	39	3.4	100	46	679
75.0	17	35	30	19	186	8.5	47	3.9	127	29	721
112.5	22	71	33	30	188	8.9	53	4.6	165	25	788
AV	18	44	30	21	181	8.5	47	4.0	131	30	729
1% FPDU											
37.5	15	15	27	7	160	7.4	29	3.5	105	48	658
75.0	16	29	29	14	166	7.5	29	3.8	122	28	693
112.5	18	41	29	17	166	8.7	50	4.3	150	23	149
Av	16	28	28	13	164	7.9	36	3.9	126	29	700
	SED	CD	SED	CD		SED	CD	SED	CD		
Control vs root	0.99	2.0	0.56	1.1		0.6	1.2	0.26	0.5		
Source × level	0.77	1.6	0.43	0.9		0.5	1.0	0.20	0.4		
Source × level	1.33	2.7	ns	–		ns	–	ns	–		

Ammonia volatilization from waterlogged soils of North Bihar

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In flooded alkaline soils, fertilizer N is lost to air as ammonia during the first few weeks of submergence. We measured ammonia volatilization with different N sources. Soil was an alkaline sandy loam Entisol with pH 8.4, 0.34% organic C, 221 kg KMnO₄-N/ha, and 31% free

CaCO₃ Urea, lac-coated urea, neem cake and urea mixed 1:1 with green manure were the N sources. Rajendra Dhan 201 was grown in a flooded field in 20-m² plots. A 1.2-cm-diam × 35-cm-tall cylindrical frame covered with plastic bag was placed between rows of rice plants immediately after N fertilizer was applied. A petri dish filled with 100 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ was suspended inside the frame. At 3-d intervals, the petri dish was emptied and the contents were distilled for NH₃ with MgO in a microkjeldahl apparatus. Volatilization loss was calculated based on area.

N losses through ammonia volatilization varied widely among N sources. After 16 d, the cumulative N loss ranged from 38 to 55 g/20 m². Volatilization loss was lowest for the urea-green manure treatment: 10 to 26% of fertilizer N volatilized within 4 d of application (see table). Rate of loss declined substantially over time. Total or cumulative loss in 16 d was between 20 and 30% with different N sources. Associated analysis of floodwater, soil solution, and wet soil indicated that high floodwater temperature, high HCO₃⁻ soil solution concentration, high soil pH, and high electrical conductivity caused high volatilization losses in North Bihar. ☞

Percent N loss through NH₃ volatilization, North Bihar, India.

Treatment ^a	% loss of N through volatilization at indicated days after fertilizer application						Cumulative loss (%) in 16d
	0-4 d	4-7 d	7-10 d	10-13 d	13-16 d		
Urea split (45 kg N/ha basal + 22.5 kg N/ha at tillering + 22.5 kg N/ha at panicle initiation)	25 15 ^b 12 ^c	1.8 19 1.8	1.9 1.9 0.4	1.3 1.4 0.8	0.3		29
Urea basal (90 kg N/ha)	26	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.3		29
lac-coated urea basal	25	2.5	1.5	1.1	0.2		30
neem cake-coated urea basal	23	3.0	0.6	0.8	0.4		28
Green manure + urea (1:1)	18	1.0	0.6	0.8	0.2		21

^aEach treatment received 45-45 kg PK/ha. ^bLoss after first urea split. ^cLoss after second urea split.

Evaluation of tractor-drawn puddlers and puddling operations

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In Haryana, most farmers with tractors use mounted, spring-loaded cultivators for puddling. Some also use mounted disk harrows. Rotary blade puddlers, rototillers, and power tillers are